

Seize the Moment

Building Library Outreach One Opportunity at a Time

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Background & Challenges

Large Healthcare System

- 7 hospitals and 65 clinics
- 7,000+ employees

Resource Constraints

- 5 full-time employees
 - My role
- Managing multiple priorities

Need for Strategic Outreach

"...you should think of your energy as if it's expensive, as if it's like a luxury item. Not everyone can afford it."

-Taylor Swift

Practical Outreach Strategies

- Start small
- Meet people where they are
- Automate
- Integrate into existing initiatives
- Don't reinvent the wheel
- Show, don't tell
- Leverage existing relationships

Real-World Examples

- Career Center Collaboration
- Crime Victim Services
- Plant Partners
- What We're Reading
- Libby

Other Considerations

- Importance of boundaries
- Meaningful connections > shouting into the void
- Point of need support builds trust and relevance

Thank you!